

NANOROBOTS IN CANCER THERAPY; A REVOLUTIONARY FRONTIER IN TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY

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ABSTRACT

Early detection and diagnosis of many cancers is very challenging. Late stage detection of a cancer always leads to high mortality rates. It is imperative to develop novel and more sensitive and effective diagnosis and therapeutic methods for cancer treatments. The development of new cancer treatments has become a crucial aspect of medical advancements. Nanobots, as one of the most promising applications of nanomedicines, are at the forefront of multidisciplinary research. With the progress of nanotechnology, nanobots enable the assembly and deployment of functional molecular/nanosized machines and are increasingly being utilized in cancer diagnosis and therapeutic treatment. In recent years, various practical applications of nanobots for cancer treatments have transitioned from theory to practice, from in vitro experiments to in vivo applications. In this paper, we review and analyze the recent advancements of nanobots in

cancer treatments, with a particular emphasis on their key fundamental features and their applications in drug delivery, tumor sensing and diagnosis, targeted therapy, minimally invasive surgery, and other comprehensive treatments. At the same time, we discuss the challenges and the potential research opportunities for nanobots in revolutionizing cancer treatments. In the future, medical nanobots are expected to become more sophisticated and capable of performing multiple medical functions and tasks, ultimately becoming true nanosubmarines in the bloodstream.

KEYWORDS: Nanorobots, Cancer treatment, Drug delivery, Targeted therapy.

Fig No. 1: raphical abstract.

INTRODUCTION

The unchecked development and spread of aberrant cells within the body is known as cancer. These cells can invade and destroy nearby healthy tissue and in many cases, spread (metastasize) to other parts of the body through the blood or lymphatic system. Or cancer is a disease in which some of the body's cells grow uncontrollably and spread to other parts of the body. Cancer can start almost anywhere in the human body, which is made up of trillions of cells. Normally, human cells grow and multiply (through a process called cell division) to form new cells as the body needs them. When cells grow old or become damaged, they die, and new cells take their place.^[1] Cancer is a disease where aberrant cells proliferate out of control and have the potential to spread to other areas of the body (spread). Normal cell division and death are not followed by these aberrant cells. Hippocrates, a Greek physician who lived from 460 to 370 BC, is credited with coining the term cancer. Hippocrates, regarded as the father of medicine, coined the terms carcinoma and carcinos. Hippocrates thought that the body could describe both ulcer-forming and non-ulcer-forming tumors. Hippocrates possessed four humors, or bodily fluids: black bile, yellow bile, phlegm and blood. According to him, an excess of black bile in different body parts combined with an imbalance of these humors could lead to diseases. This was the humoral theory.^[2]

CASUSES OF CANCER

- 1) Genetic factors
- 2) Environmental factors
- 3) Lifestyle factors
- 4) Infection
- 5) Age
- 6) Hormonal factor
- 7) Immune system function

SYMPTOMS OF CANCER

- 1) Unexplained weight loss
- 2) Fatigue and Pain
- 3) Change in skin
- 4) Change in bowel or bladder habits
- 5) Unusual bleeding or discharge
- 6) Difficulty swallowing
- 7) Lumps or swelling

Type of nanorobots

- 1) **Pharmacy:** A medical nanorobot with a diameter of 1–2 μm . Molecular indicators or chemotactic sensors are used to ensure the precision of the targeting system. They can be eliminated or recuperated through centrifuge nanapheresis after finishing the tasks.^[3]
- 2) **Microchips :** Nanorobots possess microchips which can conduct current signals once the molecules detect a disease. The benefits are the small charge to yield and simple to operate.^[4]
- 3) **Respirocyte:** A type of nanorobot that carries oxygen like an artificial red blood cell. The power is achieved through endogenous serum glucose.^[5]

Fig No. 2: Respirocyte body.

- 3) **Microbivores:** The nanorobot is flat and spheroidal in shape for nanomedical uses With a diameter of 3.4 μm along its main axis and a diameter of 2.0 μm on the minor axis It has the phagocytic capability which is almost 80 fold higher proficient than other macrophages.^[6]

Fig No. 3: Microbivores.

- 4) **Clottocytes:** They have the 'instant' hemostasis biological activity which is called artificial mechanical platelets They also transport substances that assist in the coagulation process.^[7]
- 5) **Chromalloyte:** The renovation machine will first assess the condition by inspecting the cellular substances, actions, and works These repair machines are capable of overhauling the complete cell.^[8]

NANOTECHNOLOGY

The field of science and engineering known as "nanotechnology" is dedicated to creating, creating and utilizing systems, devices, and structures through atom and molecular manipulation at nanoscale.^[9]

When it comes to technological advancements, nanotechnology has been at the forefront of taken into account and has garnered enormous attention over time. composed of metal, metal oxides, carbon, or organic substance.^[10]

A crucial component of biotechnology and medicine, nanomedicine enhances diagnosis, treatments, and illness prevention. Nanotechnology has improved healthcare and helped develop fresh approaches to illness diagnosis and treatment.^[11] Researchers are utilizing nanotechnology in medicine to enhance instruments such as sensors, diagnosticsurfaces, as well as cleaning supplies. There are new gadgets being developed that operate inside the body todiagnosis and medical care. By merging technology,

nanoengineering, and medicine, Physicians are benefiting from innovations like drug delivery systems and nanorobots for surgery. understand diseases better and find better treatments.^[12]

Chemotherapy drug delivery using nanorobots in cancer treatment

New advances in medication delivery have resulted in greater quality in targeted drug delivery that uses nanosensors to detect particular cells and regulate discharges through the use of smart medicines.^[13] Traditional chemotherapeutic drugs act by eliminating swiftly replicating cells, which is a primary feature of malignant cells. Most anticancer medications have a limited therapeutic boundary, often resulting in cytotoxicity to normal stem cells that proliferate quickly, such as bone marrow, macrophages, gastrointestinal tract (GIT), and hair follicles, causing adverse effects like myelosuppression (lower synthesis of WBCs, producing immunosuppression), mucositis (inflammation of the GIT lining), alopecia (hair loss), organ malfunction, thrombocytopenia/anaemia, and haematological side effects, among other things. Doxorubicin is used to treat numerous forms of cancer, including Hodgkin's disease, when it is combined with other antineoplastic medicines to minimize its toxicity.^[14-15] Paclitaxel is a drug that is injected intravenously and is used to treat breast cancer. Some of the significant side effects include bone marrow suppression and progressive neurotoxicity. Cisplatin is an alkylating drug that results in the intra-DNA binding filament. Its negative effects include giddiness and severe vomiting, and it can be nephrotoxic.^[16] Camptothecin is applied neoplasia by inhibiting type 1 topoisomerases, an enzyme required for cellular duplication of genetic information. Numerous initiatives have been launched with the goal of employing nanotechnology to build DDS that can reduce the negative impacts of traditional therapy. On the surface of single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs), doxorubicin was layered.^[17] Doxorubicin was used in metastatic tumour cells as a polymer prodrug/collagen hybrid. The use of polymeric pro-drug nanotechnology in the therapy of rapidly dividing abnormal cells is a novel advance in the field.^[18] Nanotechnology is continually looking for biocompatible materials that may be used as a DDS. The nanoparticle hydroxyapatite (HA), a significant component of bone and teeth, was employed to deliver paclitaxel, an neoplastmedication, and the out-turn implies that therapy should begin with hydrophobic medicin].

Fig No 3: Overview illustrating the challenges of swimming nanorobots for drug delivery and therapy,

ADVANTAGES

- It additionally minimizes surgeon mistakes. Computer-controlled drug delivery and larger speed of drug action area unit its sublimity.
- It can monitor neuro-electric signals and stimulate bodily systems.
- Nanorobots can treat and restore lost tissue at the cellular level.
- Nanobots area unit specific and correct with fewer facet effects that unleash medicine in a very controlled manner.
- Nanorobots will cure several senior ill-patients and renew their lives. HIV, cancer, and different harmful unwellness are beneath progress for the natural process.^[24] Provide speed and longevity and for drug deliver.
- Helpful for watching, identification, and fighting illness.
- Will treat and notice unwellness and restore lost tissue at the cellular level

DISADVANTAGES

- The initial design cost and installation cost is high.
- The design is very complicated and maintenance is difficult.
- The most daunting obstacle is the power supply.
- Electrical systems may create stray fields which may activate bioelectric-based molecular recognition systems in biology.

- Nanorobotics self-replicate and our immune system can be challenged if we depend a lot on nanotechnology.
- A cluster of different nanorobots is harmful.^[26]
- If the nanobots are misused by terrorists, it could even be used as bio-weapons and may become a threat to society

MECHANISM OF NANOROBOTS

The chemicals on the target's surface allow the nanorobots to recognize and recognize it. They become aware of the availability of higher sensors and nanoscale actuators. release of the substances. The NCD machine was created, a package for Nanorobots in settings where viscous and Brownian movement predominate in fluids as opposed to forces that are mechanical phenomena. Initially, in order to compare things somewhat, the scientists employed the tiny Brownian motions of the nanorobots to conduct a random search for the target. in a The nanorobots monitor for chemical concentration using an extremely second methodology. much above the amplitude. Following signal detection, a nanorobot calculates the concentration gradient and advances to a higher concentration until it hits the intended location. In the third method, nanorobots at the target release a different chemical that is used by others. as an additional signal that directs the target. Only nanorobots with these signal concentrations passing inside some microns of the target area unit doubtless to notice the signal.^[27]

Fig No. 4: Mechanism of nanorobots.

APPLICATION

- 1 Transfusions & Perfusion: Respirocytes are used because of the active oxygen-carrying component of a universally transfusable blood substitute that's free of disease vectors like hepatitis, venereal disease, malarial parasites, or AIDS.

- 2 Treatment of anemia: Respirocytes in oxygenated from help to treat all forms of anemia, including acute anemia caused by a sudden loss of blood after injury or surgical intervention.
- 3 Cardiovascular and neurovascular application: Perfusion of Respirocytes should be useful in maintaining tissue oxygenation during coronary angioplasty, organ transplantation, and Siamesetwin separation and in cardiopulmonary bypass solutions.
- 4 Tumor therapy and diagnosis: The formulation of Respirocytes are used to probe tissue oxygen tension. Respirocytes may be used as informer devices to map a patient's whole-body blood pressure or oxygenations profile storing direct sensor data on each computer.
- 5 Asphyxia: Respirocytes enhances and support breathing in case of oxygen-poor environment or where normal breathing is physically not possible.
- 6 Underwater breathing: Respirocytes can act as in vivo scuba device. Their product relives in simple of dangerous hazards of deep ocean diving caisson disease, the nitrogen bubbles are formed in blood as t diver rises to the surface, from gas previously dissolved in the blood at a higher pressure in the greater depth. Respirocytes can act as long-duration perfusion to preserve living tissues.^[28]

Fig No. 5: Application of nanorobots.

Design and Development Challenges

This section will discuss the various challenges in the design and development of nanorobots. General challenges faced in the development of nanorobots, regardless of their applications, involve:

- DNA approach that cannot be employed to develop complex devices, and

- Bacteria-based nanorobots, incorporating bacteria in the building of nanorobots, present a serious challenge, as bacteria is a living organism and therefore inappropriate due to safety reasons. Performance-wise, nanorobots depend on Brownian motion and electrical noise.^[29,30,31]
- Positional nano assembly that is inefficient in regards to building nanodevices, and this method does not incorporate nanoelectronics.

Table 1: Comparison between architecture of macro robots and nanorobots.

Architecture	Macro Robots	Nano Machines
Sensors	Temperature sensors, Light sensors, Force sensors	CMOS sensors, Nanotubes, Nanowires, Biosensors
Actuators	Pneumatic motors, Hydraulic and Electric motors	Flagella motors, DNA and RNA actuators, Protein-based motors (ATP), Liquid-crystal Elastomers (LCE's)
Navigation components	Ball bearings, Belt drives, Gears	β Sheets, sperm-like motors
Joints and Links	Prismatic, Spherical, Revolute, Cylindrical	Synthetic joints, Molecular Bonds, DNA hinges, and Nanotubes

New methods of integrating all these together to control the response or actions of a nanorobot should be proposed. For example, a different imaging technique can be used to localize the nanorobot inside the body, and that information can be used by the control system to send commands to the actuators or to navigate the nanorobot using variable magnetic fields. The traditional method of reading sensors, processing the information, and designing a control scheme to send commands to actuators to minimize the error between the desired and actual values of a parameter (e.g., velocity, position, etc.) might not be feasible to be used. The development of nanoscale components is essential to the construction of a nanorobot; however, this is hindered by technological limitations. The fabrication of a nanorobot and its application in nanomedicine is limited by two main factors: (1) the status of current technological advancements; and (2) The limitations of a nanorobot to work in micro fluids.^[32]

Nanobots in Future Frankly, nanorobotics holds such a vast scope, that a single paper can't cover it all. Hence, the focus here is limited only to its revolutionary impact on the field of medicine.

Body surveillance: Continuous monitoring of vitals and wireless transmission could be

possible using nanobots, leading to a quantum leap in diagnostics. This would also help in rapid response in case of sudden change in vitals or could warn against a possibility of a risk, such as high blood glucose in case of diabetics. Also multi-functional bots could convert themselves into stents; say to open up a blockage in an artery. The bot itself can be used as a tool, to remove unwanted materials such as blockages in the circulatory system. Nanobots could be used in large quantities inside the body to sense and repair anomalies/abnormalities. Current macroscopic robots are being programmed and tested with what is known as "swarm intelligence" in which they share information available to each one of them, pool it together, and take collective decisions

Central Nervous System (CNS): Nanobots could be used to treat the cancers in the CNS too. At times, they themselves could act as implants, replacing damaged neurons in some patients. Nanobots will also be able to perform neural surgeries as well as surgeries of the brain, with a high success rate. It would also prevent the necessity of today: drilling a hole in the skull to gain access to the brain. Nanobots can also be used to help people suffering from motor neuron diseases, as well as paralysis. Once injected into the patient, they can locate themselves at specific places in the brain, and pick up impulses which would normally be delivered to the body's motor neurons. These impulses can be used to drive external prosthetics, such as a robotic arm. Thus, it would help a lot of people from overcoming their disabilities.

Delicate surgeries: Surgeries such as those of the eye are even today performed successfully only by a few skilled surgeons. Immense risk is involved in these delicate surgeries and they require a steady hand as well as a strong constitution. It may soon be possible to take the human element of risk out of this equation. Micro surgery of the eye as well as surgeries of the retina and surrounding membranes could soon be performed using nanobots. In addition, instead of injecting directly into the eye, nanobots could be injected elsewhere in the body and guided to the eye to deliver drugs, if necessary. Similarly, other difficult surgeries will also benefit from advances in nanorobotics. Foetal surgery, risky even today due to high mortality rate of either the baby or the mother, could soon have a 100% success rate, due to the fact that nanobots can provide better access to the required area inducing minimal trauma.

Cancer treatment: This is probably the main reason for the development of nanorobotics. Drug delivery for cancer today is difficult to control. Chemotherapy harms healthy tissue in addition to cancerous tissue. We cannot prevent adverse effects of chemotherapy on other

parts of our body. Nanorobotics will change it all. Nanobots could be used to deliver drugs specifically to the tumour only, thus preventing the peripheral impact of the drug. One of the many methods to achieve this is the following: Primary nanobots are sent to the target tissue (tumour) to inflame it. This is partly a machine gun approach; a lot of the bots will be wasted. However, only the tumour is inflamed and not any other tissue in the entire body. Now, a second wave of bots is sent, to target the inflamed tissue. This wave of bots contains the actual chemotherapy drug. It releases its payload i.e. the drug only after sensing the inflamed tissue. Thus, we have a highly concentrated targeted action, with no peripheral impact. We could liken it to a sniper's rifle.

DRUG DELIVERY AND NANOTECHNOLOGY

The low bioavailability of medications can be overcome with nanotechnology. Drug delivery is greatly enhanced by the use of a nanodrug delivery system. Being extremely tiny Unlike other larger elements that are discarded, nanoparticles are absorbed by the cells. may compel a patient to take larger dosages. Conversely, with nanoparticles prolonged The medication's targeted action may be accomplished, potentially lowering the dosage. In addition, nan One benefit of drugs is their quicker dissolution, which increases their bioavailability. Tinier medication dosages that reduced toxicity and dosing variability. Among the principal effects of The creation of entirely novel drug forms is known as nanoscience.^[33]

Elements Nanobots consist of various elements to carry out their specific functions

- Control Unit- it acts as the brain of the nanobot. It receives instructions from external sources or works based on preprogrammed algorithms, it may be designed using molecular processors or nanoscale circuits.
- Power Supply- it can be obtained from different origins like internal chemical reactions (e.g., glucose in the body), external energy sources like ultrasound or magnetic fields or bio-batteries or nano-generators.
- Sensors- These identify particular changes in the environment to allow the nanobot to react accordingly. In DNA nanobots, aptamers (short RNA or DNA sequences) may be used as molecular sensors, which bind to target molecules with great specificity.
- Actuators- Actuators facilitate movement or structural changes in the nanobot. For example, DNA nanomachines can undergo conformational changes depending on certain DNA strands or external stimuli, allowing functions such as opening or closing to deliver therapeutic agents.

- **Body-** It provides shape and protection to internal components. It can be made from biocompatible materials like: Carbon-based structures (e.g., carbon nanotubes), DNA origami (folded DNA structures), diamondoid materials for rigidity.
- **Propulsion Systems-** Movements vary according to the environment and design of the nanobot. Some DNA nanobots utilize chemical energy to enable mechanical movement, hence converting chemical fuel into kinetic movement.

Fig No. 7: Elements of nanorobots.

COMPONENTS OF NANOROBOTS

The various element in nanorobot includes power supply, motors, manipulators, onboard computers, fuel buffer tank, sensors, pumps, pressure tanks, and structural support. The substructures in a nanorobot include:

- **Payload:** This section holds a small dose of drug/medicine. The nanorobots could transverse within the blood and release the drug to the site of infection/injury.^[34]
- **Micro camera:** The nanorobot may contain a miniature camera. The operator will steer the nanorobot once navigating through the body manually.^[35]
- **Electrodes:** The electrode mounted on the nanorobot can form the battery using the electrolytes within the blood. These protruding electrodes generate an electric current to kill the cancer cell and heating the cells to death.
- **Lasers:** These will burn harmful material like arterial plaque, blood clots, or cancer cells.
- **Ultrasonic signal generators:** These generators are used to target and destroy kidney stones.
- **Swimming tail:** They need propulsion to get into the body as they travel against the flow of blood within the body

Fig No 8: Structure of nanorobots.

IDEAL CHARACTERS OF NANOROBOTS

- Nanorobot working in tissue could be as large as 0.5-3 microns, whereas one in the bloodstream needs to be 500-3000 nm.^[36]
- Injection of a dose of 3 cubic cm would be acceptable for the human body.
- It can communicate with the doctor by encoding a message to acoustic signals at the radio wave frequency of 1-100 MHz. It might produce multiple copies of it to interchange units, and this method refers to as called self-replication.
- After the completion of the task, it can be retrieved by allowing it to fuse them via the usual human excretory channel or can also be removed by an active scavenger's system.
- The surface of nanorobots should be made with smooth, flawless, diamond surfaces.
- The shape should be flexible which would make it easier for the device to enter the cytoplasm, affect micro hydrodynamic stability, and more.

FUNCTIONALITY

A respirocyte would require the following elements in order to function:

- 1] Molecular rotors: Made up of about 100,000 atoms, they pump gases into and out of the storage spaces that are under pressure, and gather glucose for energy. They would function. They are unable to pump all because of their selective binding sites.
- 2] A power generator, which uses glucose, functions similarly to a fuel cell. gathered by a rotor of a selective pump to produce enough energy to run the apparatus.
- 3] Water ballast chambers: Buoyancy is managed with them.
- 4] Sensors: These are used to measure the amounts of carbon dioxide and oxygen in the nearby, and keep an eye on the pressure in the gas storage tanks. A tiny computer would

be required to use the data and interpret sensor input. to regulate the distribution of power and gas flow rates. The computer would only require modest processing power in comparison to standard-sized computers, but the computing core and the A 124 nmwide unit would need to accommodate data storage.

- 5] Pressure transducers: These devices are used to receive programming instructions that are sent by a doctor through an encoded sequence of compression pulses.^[37]
- 6] Pressure Vessel: Considering the objective of transferring oxygen from the lungs to a different body tissues, a tiny pressure vessel is the most basic type of artificial respirocyte.
- 7] Molecular Sorting Rotors: Effective respirocyte function requires an active method of transferring gas molecules between pressurized microvessels. Molecular organization There have been suggestions for rotors that might be perfect for this job. Each rotor has a binding site.alternately exposes "pockets" along the rim to the interior chamber and blood plasma by the disk's movement.
- 8] Device Scaling: Determining the maximum size of a physical device is easy because Respirocytes must be ready to enter all tissues via blood vessels. They can't be bigger than the capillaries in humans. The lowest respirocyte diameter that can be achieved is motivated byoperational requirements and by the smallest possible element size.

Figure No. 9: A proposed design for a respirocyte.

HOW IT WORKS

Molecular sorting rotors allow respiratory cells to exchange gases. The revolving possess specially designed tips to capture specific kinds of molecules. The storage of gas molecule securely inside tanks. There are three different kinds of rotors in every respirocyte. The

lungs collect oxygen or in production prior to being introduced to the body, where it is released and distributed throughout the body.

Another takes up carbon dioxide in the blood and expels it through the lungs. In the third absorb glucose from the blood, which is burned in a process akin to cellular.

The respirocyte is powered by respiration. Around the equator, twelve identical pumps were placed where the

Carbon dioxide rotors are on the left, water rotors are in the middle, and oxygen rotors are on the right.

The surface of the respirocyte has sensors for gas concentration. After the When a respirocyte travels through lung capillaries, the partial pressure of oxygen will be elevated and Since the partial pressure of carbon dioxide will be low, the onboard nanocomputer will direct the sorting rotors to release carbon dioxide molecules and load in oxygen. The water Ballast chambers help keep you buoyant. Respirocytes have a scavenging program. poisonous gases from the body, such as carbon monoxide.^[38]

WAYS IN WHICH NANOBOTS CHANGES THE FUTURE

Detect Bacteria: Nanobots will be able to detect the presence of bacteria and other microbes in the human body, which determine what kind of response should be set based on the kind of infection.

Determines the Effectiveness of Drugs: One of the biggest challenges in medicine is to figure out the effect that a particular medicine is having on the patient so that the medical expounder can tackle the problem by decreasing the side effects. Moreover, determining the effectiveness of the medicine is important because it allows the medical expounder to know how to treat the patient as early as possible.

Detect Particular Chemicals: Nanobots will be able to detect the presence of particular chemicals in the human body, which will provide crucial information to medical expounders about the condition of the patient so that it can be used to ensure more efficient and effective treatment.

Clear Blocked Blood Vessels: There is a lot of interest coming up with potential solutions as

well as potential preventatives for cardiovascular disease which is one of the most common killers. Theoretically, blockages in blood vessels that are responsible for both strokes and heart attacks can be cleared by using nanobots. But practically, if these bots are not able to wholly solve the problem, they can reduce the chances of dying from either one of those conditions, which will be an incredible improvement even.

Serve as Antibodies: Nanobots are used to boost the existing antibodies for individuals with weak immune systems who cannot manage all the bacteria and other microbes. Here, the nanobots used to potentially destroy the dangerous foreign substances in the human body. Alternatively, this consists of the nanobots that direct the existing immune processes at the sources of danger.

Clean Up Pollution: In the future, it might be possible to use nanobots to clean up pollutions, thus restoring polluted environments to a clean and virgin condition. Inspecting the impacts that pollution will cause the health of entire ecosystems together with human health. Nanobots can be considered as an inestimable boon because nanobots would be deployable in toxic sites therefore reducing the risk to human counterparts.^[39]

NEED FOR MICROBIVORE

The current therapies for a number of septicemic agents frequently need a lot of drugs that must be taken over an extended period of time, frequently achieve only partial elimination of bloodborne infections with comparatively low device dosages which can be a welcome addition to the doctor's therapeutic toolkit. That's created to address septicemia, or blood poisoning. Microbivores would belong to the medical nano-robots that target dangerous pathogens using a diamondoid arrangement of atoms inside the blood.^[40]

CONCLUSIONS

The main target of writing this review was to provide an outline of the technological development of nanotechnology in medicine by making a nanorobot and introducing it in the medication of cancer as a new mode of drug delivery. Cancer is described as a collection of diseases characterised by the unregulated development and spread of malignant cells in the body, and the number of people diagnosed every year keeps adding up. Cancer treatment is most likely the driving force behind the creation of nanorobotics; it can be auspiciously treated using existing medical technology and therapeutic instruments, with the major help of nanorobotics. To decide the prognosis and chances of survival in a cancer patient, consider

the following factors: better prognosis can be achieved if the evolution of the disease is time-dependent and a timely diagnosis is made. Another important aspect is to reduce the side effects of chemotherapy on the patients by forming efficient targeted drug delivery systems. Programmable nanorobotic devices working at the cellular and molecular level would help doctors to carry out precise treatment. In addition to resolving gross cellular insults caused by non-reversible mechanisms or to the biological tissues stored cryogenically, mechanically reversing the process of atherosclerosis, enhancing the immune system, replacing or rewriting the DNA sequences in cells at will, improving total respiratory capacity, and achieving near-instant homeostasis, medically these nanorobots have been put forward for use in various branches of dentistry, research in pharmaceuticals, and aid and abet clinical diagnosis. When nanomechanics becomes obtainable, the ideal goal of physicians, medical personnel, and every healer throughout known records would be realized. Microscale robots with programmable and controllable nanoscale components produced with nanometre accuracy would enable medical physicians to perform at the cellular and molecular levels to heal and carry out rehabilitating surgeries. Nanomedical doctors of the 21st century will continue to make effective use of the body's inherent therapeutic capacities and homeostatic systems, since, all else being equal, treatments that intervene the least are the best.

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